

Industrial Growth Analysis in Maharashtra: A Study from 2011 to 2021

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Abstract:

Maharashtra is potentially contributing from its industrial sector to the GDP of India. Study is analysing industrial growth patterns across six administrative divisions of Maharashtra—Konkan (excluding Mumbai and Mumbai Suburban), Pune, Nashik, Aurangabad, Amravati, and Nagpur—over the period from 2011 to 2020. Utilizing secondary data, the research focuses on four key sectors: manufacturing, construction, mining, and utility supply. Through comprehensive analysis, the study uncovers significant regional disparities in industrial GDP contributions. Regions such as Pune, Nashik, and have emerged as prominent industrial hubs due to favourable infrastructure and high contribution towards industrial growth of Maharashtra, while areas like Vidarbha and Marathwada face challenges with lower industrialization rates. The manufacturing sector consistently proves to be the primary driver of industrial growth, overshadowing other sectors. These findings emphasize the need for strategic policy interventions to promote balanced economic development across Maharashtra, fostering equitable growth and overall economic resilience beyond the dominant economic influence of Mumbai.

Keywords: Industry, Divisions, Manufacturing, Imbalance

Introduction

Maharashtra is India's third-largest state by area and the second-most populated, plays especially important role in economic growth of county. It is in western India with rich culture, historical significance, and urban allure, the state is also home to numerous rural communities sustaining agrarian lifestyle. Mumbai as its capital by leveraging its strategic location and well-developed infrastructure contributing very significantly to the national GDP. Maharashtra with well-established infrastructure, skilled labour force and conducive policies attracts investment at a larger pace especially in the regions of Mumbai, Thane, and Pune districts.

The industrial sector holds a critical role in economies worldwide, serving as a cornerstone for economic growth, innovation, and employment. Economically, the industrial sector significantly boosts gross domestic product (GDP) through production of goods and services for both domestic consumption and international trade. Moreover, industries are major employers, providing livelihoods to millions across various skill levels and socio-economic improvements. Maharashtra is spread across six administrative divisions—Konkan, Pune, Nashik, Aurangabad, Amravati, and Nagpur divisions, which exhibits varied patterns of growth and development. Regions like Pune, Nashik, and Aurangabad have emerged as industrial hubs with manufacturing, automotive, and pharmaceutical sectors, benefiting from favourable infrastructure and investments. In contrast, regions such as Vidarbha and Marathwada face challenges with comparatively lower industrialization rates, constrained by inadequate infrastructure, limited access to capital and dependency on agriculture.

The study is focusing on industrial growth pattern in different divisions of Maharashtra for the ten years of time year 2011 to 2021. Industrial sectors consist of manufacturing, construction, mining & quarrying and utility supply like water, gas, electricity, transportation, warehouses etc. These components collectively form the industrial sector, contributing to economic growth, employment generation, technological advancement, and infrastructure development of the country or regions.

Literature Review

Patki, A. D. (2006). Imbalance in industrial development of Maharashtra. In this analysis three regions of Maharashtra i.e. Vidarbha, Marathwada and the rest of Maharashtra have undertaken to understand the regional imbalance due to industrial growth disparity in the state. The study has used secondary data during different points of time for organised industrial sector 1981, 1991 & 1999 and unorganised sector- agricultural and no agricultural industry 1980, 1991 & 1998. Analyse the data composite index is used with equal weighted method by taking various indicators of industrial development. Measure a disparity through composite index in industrial growth between the regions study has calculated a coefficient of variation and range coefficient. It has been found that inter-regional disparity in Marathwada and Vidarbha is very high concerning industrial development, whereas the rest of Maharashtra region is significantly advanced.

C N Choubey (2015) in this study he examined industrial disparity in the state of Maharashtra division-wise and district-wise. The author has taken four indicators i.e. electricity consumption, number of factories, number of factory workers and investment in fixed capital for the two years 1999-

2000 and 2008-2009. It is found in a study that coefficient of variation (CV) is increasing in times undertaken for the study which means division wise, and district wise there is disparity in industrial growth, and it is increasing with the time. There are few divisions like Konkan and Pune which has better performance in all the four variables analysed as compared to divisions like Aurangabad and Nagpur with this there is inter-district disparity within the different regions of Maharashtra.

Suhas Vilas Kamble, Mohit Maroti Gaikwad, Prof. Ramchandra N. Gohad (2022) have suggested to setup a new MIDC in Maharashtra specially for highly imbalanced region which can help in developing of new agro-based industries for their strongest agricultural product. To find the spatial imbalance in regions of Maharashtra district wise convex hull centroid method is used by dividing a state into three sub-regions based on 285 km distance from the capital of state i.e. Mumbai. It is found that there is large intra-state imbalance in state which leads to migration mostly from rural to urban area. Few regions of Maharashtra is very dominating like Mumbai, Pune and Nagpur due to higher industrial and services development which attract large migration also leads to negative population growth, lack of job availability in other areas like Nandurbar, Gadchiroli, Gondia etc.

Research Gap: There is substantial literature on India's overall industrial growth and regional disparities, there is a noticeable gap in the detailed examination of division-wise industrial dynamics within Maharashtra. Existing studies often focus on aggregate state-level data or emphasize specific sectors without comprehensive divisional analysis. This study seeks to fill this gap by providing an exploration of industrial growth patterns across Maharashtra's six administrative divisions from 2011 to 2021 (10Years), thereby offering insights into regional variations and contributing to a deeper understanding of industrial development within the state.

Objectives:

1. To find the division wise industrial growth contribution in GDP of Maharashtra.
2. To analyse the growth in construction, mining, manufacturing and utility supply separately
3. To examine the prime sector of industrial growth in Maharashtra

Hypothesis:

HO: There are no significant differences in the industrial contribution to GDP among the administrative divisions of Maharashtra.

Industrial Gross Domestic Product at Constant Price 2011-12 (₹ crore)

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Konkan	82,878	85,827	88,674	95,935	1,04,639	1,10,783	1,14,813	1,16,128	1,09,617	1,04,638	1,08,563
Nashik	43,488	45,530	47,073	50,344	55,376	58,273	59,891	60,459	57,482	54,534	56,512
Pune	85,083	88,528	93,192	99,902	1,08,72	1,15,29	1,18,09	1,19,43	1,13,26	1,07,46	1,11,61

HO: There is no significant difference in the growth rates of construction, mining, manufacturing, and utility supply sectors in Maharashtra from 2011 to 2020.

HO: There is no prime sector contributing significantly to industrial growth in Maharashtra from 2011 to 2020.

Research Methodology

This study uses a quantitative research approach to investigate division-wise industrial growth in Maharashtra they are Konkan (excluding Mumbai, Mumbai Suburban) from year 2011 to 2020. Secondary data sourced from government publications, and statistical databases has been used for comprehensive analysis. The research focuses on four key sectors—construction, mining, manufacturing, and utility supply—examining their individual growth trajectories over the study period. Statistical tools such as Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and comparative percentage change calculations will be employed to assess sectoral trends and variations across the six administrative divisions of Maharashtra. Additionally, comparisons will be drawn between Maharashtra's industrial growth rates and national trends to evaluate relative performance. The study aims to provide empirical insights into regional industrial dynamics, contributing to informed policy recommendations and strategic interventions for balanced economic development in Maharashtra. Mumbai's economic activities are driven by sectors such as finance, services, and entertainment, which significantly different from the industrial and agricultural bases predominant in other regions like Konkan, Nashik, Pune, Aurangabad, Amravati, and Nagpur. By focusing on these non-Mumbai divisions, the analysis can better highlight sectoral strengths and weaknesses, which may hinder balanced economic growth across Maharashtra. This approach supports targeted interventions and resource allocation strategies aimed at fostering equitable development and enhancing overall economic resilience beyond Mumbai's economic influence.

Division wise industrial growth in Maharashtra:

Maharashtra state divided in six administrative divisions including thirty-six districts in it. Each division in contributing uniquely to the economy of the state. Each division has different socioeconomic conditions and pattern which leads to variation in its contribution to state GDP.

					9	0	1	6	6	7	4
Aurangabad	37,413	39,350	40,969	43,556	47,639	50,439	52,346	55,308	49,722	47,679	49,250
Amravati	20,203	21,202	22,491	24,040	26,139	28,242	30,627	29,303	27,683	25,973	28,338
Nagpur	37,411	42,995	42,309	44,220	48,016	50,394	51,664	52,744	50,199	49,520	50,210
Maharashtra	30647	32343	33470	35799	2,81,80	2,98,13	3,09,34	3,13,94	2,94,70	2,82,34	2,92,87
	6	2	8	7	9	1	1	2	3	4	3

Source: Di rectorate of Economics & Statistics, Planning Department, Government of Maharashtra, Mumbai.

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ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	5.85E+10	5	1.17E+10	181.1653	7.51E-35	2.36827
Within Groups	3.87E+09	60	64537028			
Total	6.23E+10	65				

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to examine the significance of differences in Industrial Gross Domestic Product (GDP) across the administrative divisions of Maharashtra, namely Konkan(excluding Mumbai), Nashik, Pune, Aurangabad, Amravati, and Nagpur. The results indicate a statistically significant variation in GDP among these divisions ($F(5, 60) = 181.17, p < 0.001$).

This finding suggests that the mean GDP values differ significantly between divisions, implying diverse economic performance levels across Maharashtra. The substantial F-statistic and extremely low p-value ($p < 0.001$) provide strong evidence against the null hypothesis. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there are significant differences in the industrial contribution

to GDP among the administrative divisions of Maharashtra.

Performance of Industry (construction, mining, manufacturing, and utility supply) 2011 to 2021:

The industries are firstly, the construction sector contributes significantly to infrastructure development, addressing the state's growing urbanization. Secondly, mining activities not only fulfil local demand for essential minerals but also contribute to the state's revenue through extraction and export. Thirdly, the manufacturing sector in Maharashtra is diverse and dynamic, driving industrial growth and innovation across various sectors such as textiles, pharmaceuticals, automobiles, and electronics. Finally, utility supply ensures the efficient provision of electricity, gas, and water, crucial for sustaining both urban and rural communities.

Growth Rate Based on Gross Domestic Product at Constant Price 2011-12 of Maharashtra

	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Minign & Quarrying	13.7	-38.5	8.1	22.1	-1.1	10.0	6.9	-11.3	-1.4	-1.5
Manufacturing	7.8	9.6	5.7	10.7	6.8	2.6	0.4	-7.4	-5.4	4.0
Electricity, Gas, Water & Utility Services	4.7	-4.7	15.3	4.6	3.1	10.7	1.0	-2.1	-3.3	12.3
Construction	-4.1	3.5	8.5	1.8	5.4	2.0	3.7	0.5	-2.3	1.2

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	71.56969	3	23.85656	0.254933	0.857304	2.866266
Within Groups	3368.869	36	93.5797			
Total	3440.439	39				

The ANOVA results indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the means of the groups being compared. The between-groups sum of squares (SS) is 71.56969, and the mean square (MS) is 23.85656. The F-statistic is 0.254933, which is much lower than the F critical value of 2.866266, and the P-value is 0.857304, which is significantly higher than the alpha level of 0.05. This high P-value suggests that we fail to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that any observed differences in the group means of the growth rates of construction, mining, manufacturing, and utility

supply sectors in Maharashtra from 2011 to 2020 are likely due to random chance rather than a true effect.

Prime Sector for Industrial Growth in Maharashtra:

Industrial sectors comprise with construction, manufacturing, mining & quarrying and utility supply like gas, water, transportation etc. All these sectors are contributing to growth of industries in different way. To find the contribution of most impactful sector on overall industrial State Gross Domestic Product multiple regression model is used.

Percentage Contribution in Industrial Gross Domestic Product of Maharashtra at Constant Price 2011-12

Source: Directorate of Economics & Statistics, Planning Department, Government of Maharashtra, Mumbai.

The hypothesis H0 posits that no single sector significantly contributes to industrial growth in Maharashtra from 2011 to 2020. However, the provided bar chart shows that the Manufacturing sector consistently accounts for the largest share of industrial growth, ranging from approximately 55% to 70% annually. In contrast, the Construction and Electricity, Gas, Water Supply & Other Utility Services sectors contribute significantly less, with stable percentages around 5% to 20% and 6% to 8%, respectively. This dominant and consistent contribution by the Manufacturing sector suggests

rejecting H0 indicating that Manufacturing is a prime contributor to Maharashtra's industrial growth during this period.

Conclusion:

The analysis of industrial growth across Maharashtra's divisions from 2011 to 2020 reveals significant regional disparities in economic performance. There are substantial differences in GDP contributions among divisions such as Konkan (excluding Mumbai), Nashik, Pune, Aurangabad, Amravati, and Nagpur, underscoring varied growth patterns. The regions like Vidarbha and Marathwada

lag in industrialization due to infrastructure and capital constraints. There is no significant differences in the growth rates of the construction, mining, manufacturing, and utility supply sectors but the manufacturing sector's dominant and consistent contribution indicates it as the prime driver of Maharashtra's industrial growth. This finding necessitates targeted policy interventions and resource allocation to foster balanced regional development, enhancing economic resilience beyond Mumbai's influence.

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